

Medicine Recommendation Using Machine Learning

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Abstract- Machine Learning-Based Medicine Recommendation and Disease Prediction System Using Patient Symptoms aims to revolutionize healthcare by predicting diseases and recommending medicines and precautions based solely on patient symptoms. When doctors input the patient's symptoms into the system, it leverages machine learning algorithms including Random Forest, Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Gradient Boosting to analyze the data. The system provides accurate disease predictions, suggests appropriate medicines, and offers necessary precautions, thereby aiding medical professionals in making informed decisions and improving patient care outcomes.

Keywords— Machine Learning, Medicine Recommendation, Disease Prediction, Random Forest, SVM, KNN, Gradient Boosting

I. INTRODUCTION

In the medical field, accurately diagnosing diseases and prescribing the most suitable medication and precautions based solely on a patient's symptoms is crucial for optimizing treatment outcomes and ensuring patient safety. Healthcare providers face the challenging task of delivering tailored and well-informed recommendations to patients without extensive diagnostic tests, considering symptoms. Given the intricacy and unpredictability of patient data, advanced analytical tools capable of identifying connections, patterns, and insights are indispensable for informed decision-making.

Machine learning has revolutionized the healthcare industry by offering innovative solutions to issues related to disease prediction, drug prescription, and precaution recommendations based on symptoms alone. Machine learning algorithms can scrutinize intricate patient data, detect relevant patterns, and deliver personalized disease predictions, drug recommendations, and precautions tailored to each patient's unique symptom profile, leveraging vast and diverse datasets. Moreover, machine learning has the potential to equip healthcare professionals with valuable insights, enhancing the precision of treatment strategies and ultimately elevating patient care and treatment outcomes.

Ensemble techniques such as Random Forest [1], Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) [2], and Gradient Boosting are gaining prominence among various machine learning algorithms due to their ability to boost prediction accuracy and effectively handle complex datasets. In this study, we focus on developing and implementing an ensemble approach that integrates Random Forest, SVM,

KNN, and Gradient Boosting to create a machine learning-driven medical recommendation system primarily aimed at medical practitioners. Our proposed approach aims to enhance patient care in the dynamic and intricate realm of healthcare by harnessing the advantages of ensemble learning to improve the accuracy, reliability, and personalization of disease predictions, drug recommendations, and precaution suggestions based solely on the patient's symptoms.

II. RELATED WORKS

A. Satvik Garg, Drug Recommender System Using Sentiment Analysis[3]

Patient Reviews, Using machine learning algorithms like LinearSVC, this paper introduces a drug recommender system to address medical resource shortages during the COVID-19 pandemic. The system analyzes patient reviews through vectorization techniques such as Bag-of-Words (BoW), TF-IDF, Word2Vec, and Manual Feature Analysis. It recommends appropriate drugs for diseases, achieving a 93% accuracy with LinearSVC using TF-IDF vectorization.

B. Pritam Bhuiya, Rohit Malik, Aritra Rana, Md. Ashifuddin Mondal, "Personalized Medicine Recommendation and Disease Flagging Model Based on User's Previous Orders" [4]

This paper presents a healthcare recommendation model analyzing users' medicine orders to flag potential diseases and suggest related medications. Using a mix of supervised and unsupervised machine learning algorithms, the model shows high accuracy in complex scenarios

C. Rung-Ching Chen, Jiun Yao Chiu, Cho Tsan Batj, "The recommendation of medicines based on multiple criteria decision making and domain ontology — An example of anti-diabetic medicines"[5]

This study focuses on medical prescription recommendations for diabetes treatment, given its significant impact on mortality in Taiwan. The research aims to develop a decision support system aiding doctors in drug selection. The approach combines diabetic

knowledge ontology with multiple criteria decision making (MCDM) and entropy-based patient history analysis. The system integrates these elements to suggest appropriate medications, with preliminary experiments validating its efficacy.

D. JuanZhi Qi, XinYu Wang, Tao Yang, "Traditional Chinese Medicine Prescription Recommendation Model Based on Large Language Models and Graph Neural Networks" [6] This study presents a TCM prescription model using large language models and Graph Neural Networks (GNN) to improve accuracy. By analyzing symptom-herb co-occurrence and using Graph Convolutional Networks (GCN) for embeddings, the model offers enhanced prescription recommendations, outperforming baseline models in evaluations.

E. Silpa, B Sravani, D Vinay, C Mounika, K Poorvitha, "Drug Recommendation System in Medical Emergencies using MachineLearning"[7]

This study introduces a machine learning-based drug recommendation system for medical emergencies. Utilizing patient data like symptoms and vitals, the system offers accurate and timely medication suggestions, optimizing clinical decisions and ensuring patient safety during crises.

F. Md. Mustafizur Rahman, Md. Al-Amin, Jahangir Hossain, "Machine learning models for chronic kidney disease diagnosis and prediction"[8]

This study uses eight ensemble machine learning methods to improve early detection of Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD). By tuning classifiers and employing advanced techniques like MICE imputation and Borderline-SMOTE for data handling, the research enhances CKD diagnosis accuracy, offering a significant advancement in healthcare diagnostics.

G. Md Mamun Ali, Bikash Kumar Paul, Kawsar Ahmed, et al., "Heart disease prediction using supervised machine learning algorithms:[9]

Performance analysis and comparison" This study evaluates machine learning algorithms for heart disease prediction, with Random Forest achieving 100% accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity on a Kaggle dataset. The results highlight the potential of simple machine learning methods for highly accurate heart disease prediction.

H. Nikita Bhandari, Integrative gene expression analysis for the diagnosis of Parkinson's disease using machine learning and explainable AI[10].

Integrating gene expression data from various sources, this study employs machine learning and explainable AI techniques like LASSO, Ridge regression, and SHAP-based XAI to diagnose Parkinson's disease (PD). Achieving high diagnostic accuracy with Logistic regression and Support Vector Machine, the research identifies significant biomarkers, some associated with other neurodegenerative diseases, highlighting XAI's potential in early therapeutic decisions for PD treatment

III. METHODOLOGY

The primary objective of this system is to predict diseases, recommend medicines, and suggest precautions based solely on a patient's symptoms, enabling healthcare providers to make informed decisions regarding diagnosis and treatment plans. This methodology encompasses a comprehensive process that involves the utilization of data, technology, and predictive algorithms to estimate potential medical conditions and treatment options. The methodology includes:

A. Data Collection: Collection Gathering relevant patient data such as symptoms from Training.csv to build a comprehensive dataset.

```
import numpy as np
```

```
dataset = pd.read_csv('Training.csv')
```

B. Data Preprocessing: Preparing the dataset by separating features and labels, encoding categorical data, and splitting the dataset into training and testing sets.

- i) Data Shape: The code snippet first checks the shape of the dataset to understand its dimensions. Then, it separates the dataset into features (X) and target variable (y), where 'prognosis' is the target variable.

```
dataset.shape
```

```
X = dataset.drop('prognosis', axis=1)
y = dataset['prognosis']
```

- ii) Data Label Encoding : Converting categorical disease labels to numerical format using LabelEncoder for machine learning compatibility

```
le = LabelEncoder()
le.fit(y)
Y = le.transform(y)
```

- iii) Data splitting: : Splitting the dataset into training and testing sets with a 70-30 ratio for model evaluation

```
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, Y, test_size=0.3, random_state=20)
```

C. Model Training and Prediction : A dictionary of machine learning models is created, each model is trained on the training data, and predictions are made on the test data .

```

models = {
    'SVC': SVC(kernel='linear'),
    'RandomForest': RandomForestClassifier(n_estimators=100)
    'GradientBoosting': GradientBoostingClassifier(n_estimators=100),
    'KNeighbors': KNeighborsClassifier(n_neighbors=5),
}

def get_predicted_value(patient_symptoms):
    input_vector = np.zeros(len(symptoms_dict))
    for item in patient_symptoms:
        input_vector[symptoms_dict[item]] = 1
    return diseases_list[svc.predict([input_vector])[0]]
  
```

Model Prediction Function :This function takes a list of patient symptoms, creates an input vector, and predicts the disease using the trained SVC model.

The get_predicted_value function converts patient symptoms into a binary input vector based on a symptoms_dict, predicts the disease using a trained SVC model (svc), and returns the predicted disease name from diseases_list.

F. Results

Figure 1. Output User Interface

```

for model_name, model in models.items():
    model.fit(X_train, y_train)
    predictions = model.predict(X_test)
  
```

[1]

Machine learning-based medicine recommendation systems enhance disease prediction and treatment recommendations by leveraging patient-specific parameters like age and symptoms. Using ensemble techniques such as Random Forest, SVM, KNN, and Gradient Boosting, these systems improve prediction accuracy and personalize recommendations. Our proposed ensemble approach aims to optimize medical recommendations, providing accurate and tailored disease predictions, drug prescriptions, and precautions based on patient symptoms, thereby elevating patient care and treatment outcomes.

V. REFERENCES

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